

2019 Usage Report for the IPCC DDC

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1. Summary

This report provides details of how the DDC web site, ipcc-data.org, was used in the 12 months from January 1st 2019 to December 31st 2019. The information presented here is generated using the Google Analytics service; providing a range of different statistics that cover both temporal and spatial trends. Only non-bounce sessions in which users have interacted with the website have been used in this analysis.

The annual DDC access statistics for 2019 show an increase in usage compared to 2018. The Home page remains the most commonly viewed page on the DDC. In 2019 Europe was the most active region using DDC resources.

The increase in the usage of the website following the release of the IPCC 1.5 degree report [<https://www.ipcc.ch/sr15/>] in October 2018 has been sustained.

2. Evolution of User Sessions

The number of DDC page views recorded in 2019 is significantly higher than the page views received in the previous year. Page views increased from 176,307 views in 2018 to 251,012 views in 2019.

On average the usage of the DDC during 2019 is up by 42% on the previous year, nevertheless the pattern of 2019 follows the same general behaviour as previous years, a gradual decrease into the summer months and an increase in activity again from September on. The 2019 usage is characterised by a spike of activity in the latter half of September (weeks 37 and 38) that coincided with an increase in the proportion of sessions initiated from China.

Figure1: Time series of weekly DDC page views for non-bounce sessions. The time axis is shown in weeks from January 1st. Three time series are shown: green for the period from January 1st 2019 to December 31st 2019, red for 2018 and blue for 2017.

3. Access Patterns by Page on the DDC

This page view analysis examines the 50 most visited URLs on the IPCC-DDC.

The IPCC-DDC home page remains the most commonly viewed page on the DDC, receiving 16% of page views in 2019 (figure 3). Other popular pages are those that explain some of the basic science behind climate change such as: Understanding the observational record; Projected emissions and concentrations of carbon dioxide. It is clear that users are interested in using the DDC to access data and information about the IPCC 5th Assessment Report (AR5).

Figure 4 shows the number of unique page views and number of entrances for the most used pages on the DDC during 2019. Users tend to arrive at pages where the number of entrances are about

equal to the number of page views and navigate to pages where the number of entrances are much less than the number of page views.

Most users arriving at the DDC do so via the Home page. It is reassuring to know that the first DDC page users generally see is our home page because this is where we provide information about the purpose of the site and an overview of the content that we provide. Information pages about the scenario process for AR5 and the description of RCPs are also places of entry to the DDC.

Most users visiting the guidance pages navigate there from another page on the DDC, this fits with the behaviour of a person who, having found some interesting data, decides to use our guidance documents to learn how to use it.

The pageview statistics for pages hosted by the Socioeconomic Data and Applications Centre (SEDAC) is shown in Table 2 and Figure 5.

Figure 3: Distribution of page views for the most visited pages on the IPCC-DDC during 2019.

Page on the DDC	URL	Number of Views	%
Home	www.ipcc-data.org/index.html	40,062	15.96
Observations	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/index.html	20,639	8.22
CO2	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/ddc_co2.html	13,478	5.37
Simulations	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/index.html	11,047	4.40
AR5 GCM data	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/AR5/index.html	8,181	3.26
Climate Model Output	www.ipcc-data.org/sim/gcm_monthly/index.html	7,506	2.99
AR4 Observations	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/clim/ar4_global.html	7,484	2.98
Scenario Process for AR5: RCPs	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/RCPs.html	6,457	2.57
Regional Scatter Plots	www.ipcc-data.org/syn/tar_scatter/index.html	6,091	2.43
Environmental Data and Scenarios	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/ddc_envdata.html	5,423	2.16
Guidance	www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/index.html	5,371	2.14
Climate Observations	www.ipcc-data.org/observ/clim/index.html	5,128	2.04
Scenario Process for AR5	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/index.html	4,295	1.71
What is a GCM?	www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/pages/gcm_guide.html	4,211	1.68
IPCC AR5 Observed Climate Change Impacts: Map	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/observed_ar5/index.html	4,037	1.61

Table 1: Distribution of page views for the most visited pages on the IPCC-DDC during 2019. This table contains the same information as the pie chart in figure 3 but with the page URLs shown.

Figure 4: The number of unique views per page (blue) and the number of entrances per page (red) during 2019. Users tend to arrive at pages where the number of entrances are about equal to the

number of page views and navigate to pages where the number of entrances are much less than the number of page views.

Note that the “unique page views” statistic lists all pages that are visited in a session, it does not take into account the number of times a page is visited during that session.

SEDAC Page	SEDAC URL	Page views	Unique Page views	Entrances
Scenario Process for AR5: RCPs	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/RCPs.html	3,407	1,922	1,253
Scenario Process for AR5: RCPs	sedac.ipcc-data.org/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/RCPs.html	3,050	1,580	1,285
Scenario Process for AR5	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/index.html	2,934	1,895	1,216
IPCC AR5 Observed Climate Change Impacts: Map	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/observed_ar5/index.html	2,747	1,834	1,032
Socio-Economic Baseline Dataset	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/baseline/index.html	2,113	1,266	680
SRES Emissions Scenarios	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/sres/index.html	2,022	1,102	690
Socio-Economic Data and Scenarios	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/index.html	1,761	892	752
IPCC AR5 Observed Climate Change Impacts	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/observed_ar5/ar5_2.html	1,410	760	25
Scenario Process for AR5	sedac.ipcc-data.org/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/index.html	1,361	916	527
IPCC AR5 Observed Climate Change Impacts	sedac.ipcc-data.org/ddc/observed_ar5/index.html	1,290	880	518
IPCC AR4 Observed Climate Change Impacts: Map	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/observed/index.html	1,048	768	148
The IPCC and Scenario Development	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/ipcc_scenarios.html	984	718	102
Socio-Economic Baseline Dataset	sedac.ipcc-data.org/ddc/baseline/index.html	948	535	290
Parallel Phase: Climate Modelling Activities	sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ddc/ar5_scenario_process/parallel_climate_modeling.html	823	640	31

Table 2: Distribution of page views for the most visited DDC pages hosted by the Socioeconomic Data and Applications Centre (SEDAC).

When analysing the SEDAC hosted pages of the DDC it became apparent that there were a number of instances where a page had two URLs that resolved to the same content. Such pages were accessible via two domains: sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/ and obc2019/. Google Analytics statistics treat such pages individually so the effect of having two routes to the content has been to downgrade the importance of these pages.

Fortunately the dual access routes to the SEDAC pages were noted in time to be able to include statistics for both domains when reporting on the IPCC-DDC page usage in this report.

Figure 5: The number of unique views per page (blue) and the number of entrances per page (red) for the SEDAC hosted pages of the DDC. In this plot URLs that resolve to pages with the same content have been combined.

4. Geographical Distribution of Engagement with the DDC

In 2019 Europe was the most active region using DDC resources (Figure 5).

Figure 7 names the top 17 countries that make use of the DDC. Users in 6 countries account for 51% of all sessions: USA 19%, China 9%, UK 7%, India 6%, Germany 5%, Canada 5%. “other” countries not listed here account for 26% of user sessions. A full breakdown by country of the DDC user sessions in 2019 and 2018 is shown in appendix A.

Figure 6: The geographical distribution of IPCC-DDC sessions by continent for 2019.

Figure 7: The geographical distribution of IPCC-DDC user sessions by country for 2019.

Sessions initiated by users in Europe, Asia and North America account for 86% of DDC activity (figure 6) however approximately half of the DDC sessions are initiated by users in just six countries (down from 11 countries in 2018).

5. Browser Statistics

The IPCC-DDC site is available and accessible to all the major internet browsers and operating systems. English is the most used language setting, accounting for 59% of sessions (figure 8). Chrome is the most popular browser, accounting for 68% of sessions and Windows is the most popular operating system, accounting for 73% of sessions (figure 9).

Figure 8: Language settings for DDC user sessions during 2019.

Figure 9: Browser and technology characteristics of DDC user sessions with information about Browsers, Operating Systems that are used to access the DDC during 2019.

Appendix

A full breakdown, by country, of the DDC user sessions during 2019 and also during 2018 for comparison.

Country	2019 Sessions	2018 Sessions	Country	2019 Sessions	2018 Sessions
United States	9948	7159	Thailand	283	335
United Kingdom	4495	3132	Philippines	278	229
China	3570	4048	Greece	275	211
India	3114	2417	Argentina	262	163
Germany	2669	1552	Singapore	250	203
Canada	2412	1724	Russia	245	212
France	1761	1070	Poland	234	124
Australia	1488	950	Ireland	226	153
Italy	1418	918	Peru	205	171
Spain	1346	868	Bangladesh	171	146
Brazil	1200	881	Vietnam	171	129
Japan	1199	748	Nigeria	161	154
Netherlands	1185	751	Czechia	153	44
Iran	957	580	Ecuador	144	88
Sweden	852	573	Kenya	143	146
Switzerland	659	392	(not set)	119	102
South Korea	576	580	Hungary	113	69
Belgium	569	216	Egypt	108	130
Mexico	545	410	Nepal	107	86
Indonesia	482	373	Dominican Republic	103	12
Denmark	434	271	Morocco	94	186
Taiwan	425	428	Tanzania	92	60
Chile	393	195	Romania	82	78
Colombia	384	310	Israel	78	42
Ethiopia	382	283	Ukraine	74	50
Finland	374	170	Sri Lanka	70	96
Norway	359	194	Costa Rica	66	73
Turkey	357	342	Luxembourg	60	32
Portugal	343	340	Côte d'Ivoire	59	48
Austria	342	195	Saudi Arabia	58	102
Hong Kong	314	220	Mozambique	58	16
South Africa	311	254	Ghana	57	42
New Zealand	296	157	United Arab Emirates	57	78
Malaysia	291	289	Uganda	56	43
Pakistan	290	286	Cambodia	56	33

Country	2019 Sessions	2018 Sessions	Country	2019 Sessions	2018 Sessions
Jordan	54	41	Burkina Faso	17	15
Iraq	53	71	Qatar	17	8
Algeria	53	63	Fiji	16	20
Zimbabwe	48	53	Jamaica	16	13
Bolivia	48	64	Togo	16	7
Tunisia	46	159	Belarus	15	9
Trinidad & Tobago	44	26	Georgia	15	12
Myanmar (Burma)	43	37	Honduras	15	41
Guatemala	43	25	Nicaragua	15	12
Bulgaria	41	132	Kazakhstan	14	54
Slovakia	40	22	Venezuela	14	17
Senegal	40	34	Bosnia & Herzegovina	14	5
Croatia	38	22	Mauritius	14	10
Estonia	38	16	Malta	13	23
Lithuania	37	19	Kosovo	13	2
Slovenia	37	24	Botswana	12	28
Brunei	36	19	Congo - Kinshasa	12	6
Sudan	34	28	Oman	11	13
Iceland	33	12	Uzbekistan	11	24
Paraguay	33	12	Guyana	11	10
Madagascar	33	39	Mongolia	11	7
Cameroon	32	52	Lesotho	11	10
Cyprus	32	22	Namibia	10	19
Lebanon	28	30	Palestine	10	
Latvia	26	15	Réunion	9	5
Syria	26	15	El Salvador	9	14
Serbia	25	47	North Macedonia	9	4
Panama	24	23	Azerbaijan	8	10
Rwanda	24	14	Macao	8	8
Laos	23	10	Afghanistan	8	12
Uruguay	19	18	Malawi	8	13
Zambia	19	24	Papua New Guinea	8	10
Puerto Rico	19	7	Antigua & Barbuda	8	1
Niger	19	9	Djibouti	7	14
Benin	18	37	Faroe Islands	7	1

Country	2019 Sessions	2018 Sessions	Country	2019 Sessions	2018 Sessions
Kuwait	7	5	Chad	2	4
Bahrain	7	4	Timor-Leste	2	4
French Guiana	7	2	Andorra	1	1
Moldova	7		Anguilla	1	
Barbados	7	2	Burundi	1	5
Albania	6	8	Bahamas	1	3
Bhutan	6	9	Cook Islands	1	
Kyrgyzstan	6	2	Micronesia	1	2
Cuba	6	8	Gabon	1	1
Liechtenstein	6		Guernsey	1	
Comoros	5	7	Guinea	1	1
Belize	5	5	Guinea-Bissau	1	
Haiti	4	2	Jersey	1	1
Libya	4	5	Mauritania	1	4
Mali	4	9	Seychelles	1	
Sierra Leone	4	6	British Virgin Islands	1	
Suriname	4	3	U.S. Virgin Islands	1	2
Eswatini	4		Vanuatu	1	2
Armenia	3	8	Cape Verde		5
Grenada	3		Swaziland		4
Monaco	3		Dominica		3
Montenegro	3		Turkmenistan		3
Martinique	3		Greenland		2
Somalia	3	2	French Polynesia		2
Yemen	3	12	Eritrea		1
Angola	2	4	Kiribati		1
Bermuda	2		Solomon Islands		1
Curacao	2		San Marino		1
Gibraltar	2		South Sudan		1
Gambia	2	1	St. Vincent & Grenadines		1
Guadeloupe	2				
Cayman Islands	2				
Liberia	2	3			
Maldives	2				
New Caledonia	2	1	Total	52286	39402